

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PROVERBS AS A BRANCH OF PHRASEOLOGY

Abbasova L.

Azerbaijan University of Languages

Abstract

The article deals with proverbs as a field of linguistics. The general information about the phraseology has been given in the article. The field has been introduced to begin starting from the second half of the 20th century. V.V. Vinogradov has been mentioned as a linguist investigating phraseology in linguistics in the article. His articles such as "Basic concepts of Russian phraseology", "On the main types of phraseological units of the Russian language" have been touched upon in the article. The article reveals the meanings of the term of phraseology that is used in linguistics. The meanings of phraseology includes these types: a branch of linguistics that studies the modern state and historical development of the phraseological composition of a language; a set of phraseological units (phraseologisms) specific to a particular language; a set of specific word usage methods specific to a particular social group, individual wordsmiths, or literary and artistic movement.

The article mainly focuses on the field of phraseology named proverbs. It is reported in the article that phraseology has many research areas. Among them are proverbs, sayings, idioms, etc.

The article considers proverbs to occupy an important place in the creativity of any people. Proverbs are reported to be used in philology to express a specific concept. Depending on the situation, an expression, a word, used in its original place, enters the language as a proverb. It is revealed in the article that proverbs are used to express an idea in a vivid, meaningful, figurative and concrete way.

Keywords: phraseology, field, proverbs, meaning, national, structure.

Phraseology has been a distinct field of linguistic inquiry since the second half of the 20th century. In 1946, V.V. Vinogradov published an article titled "*The Main Concepts of Russian Phraseology*", followed in 1947 by another article, "*On the Main Types of Russian Phraseological Units*" [1, p. 120]. These works attracted the attention of linguists due to the complexity and relevance of the issues they raised. Following the publication of Vinogradov's articles, phraseology began to be studied intensively in all the national languages of the Soviet Union.

When referring to phraseological theory, one should in fact consider the history of phraseological thought [1, p. 100]. This theory began to take shape prior to Vinogradov and continued to develop after him.

In linguistics, the term *phraseology* is used in the following senses:

1. A branch of linguistics that studies the current state and historical development of a language's phraseological system.
2. The corpus of phraseological units (phraseologisms) belonging to a particular language.
3. A collection of characteristic linguistic expressions associated with a specific social group, individual writer, or literary movement.

The science of phraseology deals with the identification of phraseological units, the methods of their study, their classification, and their representation in dictionaries. Since phraseological combinations are introduced into speech as ready-made units and exhibit specific lexical-syntactic relations and usage characteristics in discourse, their study is also closely linked to text linguistics. Therefore, the field of phraseology can be viewed as being in close connection with the theory of literary texts. Phraseology

encompasses many areas of research, including proverbs, sayings, idioms, and more.

Proverbs hold an important place in the folklore and creative expression of any people. In philology, they are employed to convey specific ideas. A well-placed, situationally appropriate phrase or expression can become widely recognized as a proverb. Proverbs are used to express thoughts in a vivid, meaningful, figurative, and concrete manner [2, p. 4]. However, these characteristics alone do not fully capture the essence of what constitutes a proverb. After all, sayings also share these same features: they are uttered in specific and typical contexts, are situationally appropriate, and express ideas vividly and figuratively. On the other hand, the idea that any phrase uttered in a particular context could become a proverb is also subject to doubt.

In the 1960s, differing perspectives on proverbs divided Soviet linguists into two camps concerning their place in phraseology: those with a narrow approach and those with a broader approach. The former did not recognize the linguistic status of proverbs, while the latter accepted them as phraseological units [3, p. 138]. This dichotomy persists to this day. Researchers in phraseology continue to debate whether proverbs should be considered a part of phraseological combinations. Some linguists exclude proverbs from phraseology altogether, while others remain undecided.

A.V. Kunin refers to proverbs and other idiomatic sentence-type expressions as "communicative phraseological units" [4, p. 48]. According to him, proverbs and sayings that are constant in their lexical composition, convey a unified meaning, possess nominative characteristics, and function as complex components within a sentence are included among phraseologisms [4, p. 48].

Proverbs and sayings are often conflated or considered essentially the same, though opinions about

their structural characteristics may differ. For example, G. Mammadova and K. Mammadova initially argue that proverbs “are predicative in nature in terms of both meaning and structure and cannot be distinguished from regular sentences.” Yet, they also write that “not all proverbs and sayings are identical in terms of structure and function. From this perspective, they can be divided into two groups: 1) proverbs and sayings with nominative function; 2) proverbs and sayings with communicative function... Proverbs and sayings with communicative function meet all the criteria of a sentence. These are purely syntactic units. Proverbs and sayings with nominative function, on the other hand, are closer to phraseologisms in nature” [5, p. 47].

It is not entirely accurate to express a generalized opinion regarding the structural features of proverbs and sayings. While sayings may appear either as word combinations or complete sentences in terms of structure, all proverbs manifest exclusively in sentence form. Even those proverbs whose predicative character is not immediately apparent are, in fact, structured as full sentences, with their predicativity present in an implicit manner. Thus, the concept of a “nominative function” proverb is fundamentally flawed, and the claim by the aforementioned authors can be considered incorrect.

We concur with M.M. Mirzaliyeva’s assertion that “the development of phraseology follows a trajectory from word to sentence, and is associated with the process of phraseologization” [6, p.11]. Indeed, phraseology covers structures from the “word + word” model up to full sentences, and in its later development, extends even toward the level of text. Within this progression, proverbs are classified as syntactic constructions in sentence form.

V.A. Gordlevsky, discussing the role and importance of proverbs in language, eloquently notes that these expressions—symbols of folk wisdom—enter the bloodstream with a mother’s milk and are used whenever people speak about various aspects of life. “For the Ottomans—or for any Turk, for that matter—a proverb is the most precious legacy inherited from their ancestors. By calling them ‘atlar sözü’ (words of the forefathers), Turks express their special reverence for these expressions. This is not all: for Turks, just as religion is sacred, so too are proverbs” [7, p.267].

These remarks aptly reflect the significance of proverbs in language and their high esteem in the collective consciousness of a people. The term “atlar sözü” itself conveys this reverence, implying that these expressions are a sacred inheritance from forefathers, lovingly preserved and passed down.

The vast majority of proverbs are documented in the oldest and most refined written monuments of each nation. Nevertheless, it is important to note that even in cultures where ancient written traditions are absent or not well-known, a considerable number of proverbs have been created and survived into modern times. This may suggest that such peoples once possessed ancient manuscripts that were lost due to historical circumstances, while the wise expressions embedded within them continued to live on through oral

transmission. Such proverbs can rightly be considered examples of folkloric aphorisms.

Furthermore, observations show that not all aphoristic expressions found in ancient written sources were preserved as proverbs, and some proverbs that were eventually recorded as phraseologisms underwent historical lexical and morphological transformations. However, these changes typically do not occur within short periods; rather, they unfold gradually over long historical processes. Usually, such expressions are transmitted unchanged across generations, both in terms of structure and lexical composition, and only after multiple generational transitions do certain modifications appear—often without being noticed by the speakers themselves. It is only through comparing modern versions of proverbs with their earlier written forms that we can detect such transformations.

Proverbs can be classified according to their origin as follows:

a) Authentic, purely national proverbs, for example:

New Lords, new laws; Fretting cares make gray hairs; A man is as old as he feels, and a woman as old as she looks; A wise man changes his mind, a fool never; A living dog is better than a dead lion.

Hamı gedir, quş gətirir, saqqulu bayquş gətirir; Hər oxuyan Molla Pənah olmaz; Yatma tülkü daldasında, qoy yesin aslan səni; İki qoçun başı bir qazanda qaynamaz; İgid odur, atdan düşə atlana, igid odur, hər əzaba qatlana, etc.

Such proverbs differ from other phraseological units due to their reflection of national realities and the deep connection they reveal between language and national thought. As one paremiology researcher notes, “in such examples, the lexemes marked by national characteristics are most notably proper nouns, particularly anthroponyms, toponyms, hydronyms, and ethnonyms, which form the semantic and emotive-expressive core of proverbs and sayings. In addition, realia associated with national life, culture, and history—such as exoticisms, historicisms, archaisms, and occasionalisms—also play a central role. Overall, the traditional and folkloric nature of nationally marked paremiological units is a defining feature” [8, p.9].

b) Borrowed Proverbs:

Some proverbs in a language are of foreign origin, for example:

Every Majnun praises his own Layla (of Arabic origin);

Even walls have ears (of Arabic origin);

Moscow wasn’t built in a day (of Russian origin), etc.

Often, the lexical composition of such proverbs includes at least one element that signals their foreign origin.

c) International Proverbs:

These are proverbs found in multiple languages with nearly identical meanings. Examples include:

No bees, no honey; no work, no money—He who does not work, shall not eat;

The dogs bark, but the caravan moves on—Dogs bark, but the caravan passes;

Murder will out—You can’t hide an awl in a sack;

Dog does not eat dog-A dog doesn't step on another dog's foot;

Roll my log and I'll roll yours-One hand washes the other, and both wash the face;

It is not lost that comes at last-Better late than never;

Don't cross the bridges before you come to them-Don't jump before reaching the river;

He who pays the piper calls the tune-He who pays gets to play the flute [9, p.94].

Such proverbs are typically found with similar meaning and structure in three or more different languages.

B. Dominguez expressed fascination with the similarities and parallels among the proverbs of various peoples. In his book, he grouped proverbs thematically, rather than alphabetically, arguing that alphabetical classification lacked scientific value. His contributions have inspired numerous scholarly and popular studies [10, p.128].

Dominguez devoted his research to the lexicon of proverbs, specifically that of Russian. He categorized the lexicon into two primary groups: the general vocabulary of the Russian language and dialectal vocabulary. He also considered the presence of borrowed words in proverbs as natural, linking their occurrence to Russia's historical trade relations with both the East and West. One remarkable feature of his work is the focus on word-formation mechanisms unique to proverbs [11, p.18].

The place and status of proverbs within the lexical system of language has long been a subject of inquiry among linguists. The works of H. Haas are particularly noteworthy in this regard. Haas asserts that "the proverb, as a type of phraseological unit, must find its place" within the structure of language [12, p.319]. According to him, proverbs-like other phraseological units-are not created spontaneously in speech from individual words but are introduced into discourse as ready-made expressions.

A.S. Aksomitov, in his analysis of the lexicon of proverbs, identifies three primary lexical categories:

1. Words from the core vocabulary of the Belarusian language that retain their meanings in contemporary usage;

2. Words that, in addition to contributing aphoristic meaning to the proverb, are also used individually for expressive or figurative effect;

3. Words with phraseologically bound and metaphorical meanings, which occur only in specific and stable word combinations [13, p.17].

He also classifies the lexical items used in proverbs according to their domains of use: domestic vocabulary and socio-political vocabulary. His research presents noteworthy findings regarding the literary integration of certain lexical and phraseological units originating from proverbs.

In recent decades, the proverbs of Turkic languages have also drawn increasing scholarly attention. Despite this growing interest, the precise position of proverbs within the linguistic system remains unsettled. Some researchers include proverbs within the domain of phraseology, treating them as

language units in their own right, while others argue that proverbs should be studied independently, outside the framework of standard language structures. The literature on this debate is vast and cannot be exhaustively listed here.

Linguists who consider proverbs part of phraseology often base their view on the figurative usage of words within proverbs. They point to idioms such as *to throw down one's head*, *to return empty-handed*, *to keep a clean mouth*, *to veil the eyes*, *to talk from the tip of the nose*, *to sink ships in the sea*, etc., where the component words depart from their literal meanings. Similarly, in proverbs like *A barley-fed horse travels long distances*, *Watering an empty well won't fill it*, or *Count your chickens in the fall*, the meanings of the words are metaphorical.

However, although many proverbs-like idioms-exhibit metaphorical characteristics, important distinctions remain. First, not all proverbs contain metaphorical elements, meaning figurativeness is not a universal trait. Second, the figurative nature of idioms cannot be equated with that of proverbs. In idioms, individual words usually acquire non-literal meanings, while in proverbs, it is not the individual words but the entire expression that conveys a metaphorical or ethical-philosophical message.

The metaphorical meaning of a proverb arises not from the figurative use of each individual word it contains, but rather from the fact that the proverb, as a whole, functions as a unit of figurative expression. In other words, it is not the metaphoric use of component words that causes the proverb to be metaphorical; rather, the proverb's figurative character causes the words within it to deviate from their literal meanings.

In non-figurative proverbs, all components retain their literal lexical meanings and maintain a direct connection to their referents. In such units, the absence of imagery is often compensated for by other expressive devices—such as paradox, irony, and oxymoron. Paradox, in particular, is a typical feature of paremias with varying degrees of imagery and carries strong expressive value. For example: *"It is acceptable for a thief to steal from another thief"* [8, p. 6].

In the 1960s, I. Ibrahimov wrote about proverbs and sayings. While noting that "the most important factor ensuring the artistic quality of a proverb is language," the author also presented a number of vague and imprecise statements. For instance, he writes:

"When speaking about the morphological and syntactic structure of proverbs, it is unnecessary to address their phonetic characteristics or the participation of parts of speech within them. First, proverbs do not possess unique or distinct phonetic features exclusive to them. Second, the relationship of proverbs to parts of speech is so self-evident that further discussion is unwarranted. It is enough to say that both primary and secondary grammatical categories of the Azerbaijani language are present in proverbs and sayings" [14, p. 163].

However, careful observations reveal that proverbs often exhibit characteristic phonetic features, such as alliteration, assonance, and rhythm. For example:

Might is right; It is not lost that comes at last; Every bullet has its billet; You can't eat your cake and have it; or in Azerbaijani: *El gücü, sel gücü*. These are clear instances of paronomasia—sound-based wordplay—demonstrating how phonetic similarity contributes to expressiveness. Y.N. Vinarskaya has shown that the impact of information can be enhanced through the use of sound patterns, especially alliteration and assonance. In such cases, sound functions as a formal means of creating expressiveness [15, p. 78].

The same can be said about the issue of “parts of speech in proverbs.” Some parts of speech appear frequently in proverbs, while others occur rarely, depending on their function and syntactic compatibility.

Another notable aspect is the use of proverbs across different genres of discourse—literary, political, journalistic, and beyond. The integrity of such texts as creative products is a result of compositional intentionality and the deliberate use of stylistic techniques and structural schemes. In this process of integration, the selection of text elements that best complement the overall content becomes crucial. Proverbs often play a key role in this selection. However, their effective use in text construction depends not only on their inclusion but also on how appropriately and strategically they are employed.

References

1. Виноградов В.В. Избранные труды. М.: Наука, 1975, 420 с.
2. Adilov M. Qanadlı sözlər. Bakı: Yazıçı, 1988, 438 s.
3. Бондаренко Г.В. Представление структуры текста как иерархической системы суперсинтаксических единиц // Текст и аспекты его рассмотрения. М., 1977, с. 208-217.
4. Сарсенбаев Р. Лексико-стилистические особенности казахских пословиц и поговорок. Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. Алма-Ата, 1961, 28 с.
5. Məmmədova G., Məmmədova K. İngilis dilinin frazeologiyasında atalar sözləri və onların semantik xüsusiyyətləri // Filologiya məsələləri. 2007, № 1, s. 45-51.
6. Mirzəliyeva M.M. Türk dilləri frazeologiyasının nəzəri problemləri: Fil. elm. dok. ... dis. avtoref. Bakı, 1996, 40 s.
7. Гордлевский В.А. Из истории османской пословицы и поговорки // Избранные сочинения. Том II. М.: ИВЛХ, 1961, 322 с.
8. Ясюкевич Е.Н. Паремия как феномен языка: Образно-смысловой и модально-синтаксический уровни организации (на материале русских и английских пословиц и поговорок): Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. Минск, 2003, 21 с.
9. Mustafayeva S.B. Everyday English Idioms with Azerbaijani equivalents. Baku: Letterpress, 2008, 344 p.
10. Dominguez B. E. The function of proverbs in discourse. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 2010, 220 p.
11. Булатов М., Порудоминский В. Собирал человек слова, М.: Детская литература, 1966, 224 с.
12. Haas H. Proverb familiarity in the United States: Cross-regional comparisons of the paremiological minimum. //Journal of American Folklore, 2008. p.319-347.
13. Аксомитов А.С. Лексика белорусских пословиц XIX века в связи с общей фразеологией: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. М., 1958, 50 с.
14. İbrahimov İ. Atalar sözü və məsəllər. Azərbaycan şifahi xalq ədəbiyyatına dair tədqiqlər. Bakı, 1961, s. 163-176.
15. Винарская Е.Н. Выразительные средства текста. М.: Высшая школа, 1989, 136 с.